

CODEN [USA] : IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

ASSESSMENT OF PREVALENT RISK FACTORS OF TYPE-2 DIABETES MELLITUS AND STRENGTH OF ASSOCIATION OF THESE RISK FACTORS WITH THE OCCURRENCE OF DISEASE

¹Dr Bushra Ghaffar, ²Dr Wajeaha Naveed, ³Dr Muhammad Ahsan Zeeshan Ali

¹Multan Medical and Dental College, Multan

²Mayo Hospital Lahore

³Allied Hospital Faisalabad

Article Received: June 2020

Accepted: July 2020

Published: August 2020

Abstract:

Objective: The common type of diabetes is Type-2 DM (Diabetes Mellitus). This problem normally occurs after 40 years of age. In most of the Asian region, there is high prevalence of the risk factors and in combination with this, there is also unawareness about Diabetes Mellitus and perception lack about this particular complication. The objective of this research work was to evaluate different prevalent risk factors both modifiable and non-modifiable of Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus and to provide an estimation of the strength of relationship of these particular factors and the prevalence of this complication.

Methodology: This research work was carried out at Nishter Hospital Multan. We used a Performa to gather the data from the patients and healthy controls. A sum of 300 patients of Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus and 600 healthy controls were the participants of this research work.

Result: Total 54.330% patients were present in the age group of 41 to 50 years. Approximately 69.660% patients were men and 30.340% patients were females. We found a statistically significant association between the Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus and modifiable risk factors, whereas there was no association between non-modifiable risk factors like age and gender with the Type- Diabetes Mellitus.

Conclusion: Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus is a disease with many risk factors. It is chronic in nature.

Keywords: Chronic, Diabetes Mellitus, Diabetes, Type-2, Risk Factors, Modifiable.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Bushra Ghaffar,

Multan Medical and Dental College, Multan

QR code

Please cite this article in press Bushra Ghaffar et al, Assessment Of Prevalent Risk Factors Of Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus And Strength Of Association Of These Risk Factors With The Occurrence Of Disease., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(08).

INTRODUCTION:

Around 250 BC, Diabetes Mellitus was described in Ayurveda having names of Prameha and Madhumeha [1]. Arateus described this disease in the Greek medicine field as melting down of limbs and flesh into urine [2]. This abnormality is the net deficiency of the insulin. It is only hormone which lowers the glucose in blood. Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus is the outcome of the abnormal secretion of insulin and hindrance to its action. It appears gradually when there is failure in human body to use the produced insulin efficiently. It normally starts after the age of 40 years [3]. Estimated prevalence of diabetes worldwide in year of 2010 was 285.0 million corresponding to 6.40% adult population of the world. By the year 2030, there is expectation that 438 million (7.80%) adult population of the world will suffer from diabetes. In India, it will reach to 87.0 million in year of 2030 [4]. India is recently the capital of this disease in whole world because of high number of patients in the country [5]. With the modification in the environment, it is possible to prevent 80% prevalence of Type- 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Due to the deficiency in the control program's application, its occurrence in the whole world is continuously rising [6]. This research work was carried out to determine the various risk factors for Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus in our region and association between the prevalence of this disease and risk factors to overcome the increasing issue.

METHODOLOGY:

The duration of this study was from May 2019 to June 2020. This research work was carried out at Nishter Hospital Multan. The estimation of the size of samples was carried out by utilizing 40.0% rate of prevalence with allowable error of 15.0% and the sample size came two hundred and sixty-six. We selected 300 patients by random method of sampling. Diabetes Mellitus is normally an asymptomatic complication. The early identification of this disease depends upon the behavior and perception of the human. So, it is hard to calculate the reliable rate of incidence. We took 40.0% rate of prevalence for the calculation in accord with predictable prevalence cited by WHO [7]. We selected two healthy controls for one patient. We selected 600 healthy controls from same hospital. We used a Performa for the collection of the data. We explained all the questions to the subjects of the

research work. We assured the total confidentiality to all the patients. We obtained the approval from Ethical Committee of the hospital. We recorded the blood pressure of the patients with the utilization of the mercury sphygmomanometer in sitting position. We measured the height of every subject. We also measured the weight of the patients with standard weighing machine. With the help of measuring tape, we measured the waist circumference and we also measured the circumference of waist around the mid region of buttocks.

We included all the patients who were suffering from Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus having more than 40 years of age from both genders. We included only the willing subjects in this research works. We selected the controls from the hospital with more than 40 years of age from both genders and present without Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus. we obtained the written consent from the patients and controls. We did not include the patients who were not willing to participate in this research work. All the patients suffering from other type of diabetes and having less than 40 years of age, pregnant females and seriously ill patients got exclusion from this research work. We also excluded the pregnant females, persons having less than 40 year of age and seriously ill persons from the control group. We entered the information in an excel sheet. We utilized the SPSS V.21 for analysis of collected information. We also used C 2-test and odd ratios for statistical analysis.

RESULTS:

Most of the subjects were present in the age group having >50 to 60 years in both groups, about 55% study population. This age group was followed by the subjects having >40 to 50 years age, about 35.0% of total population of study. Old subjects (>60 to 70 years) and very old persons (greater than 70 years of age) accounted for approximately 10.670% in both groups. We recorded the minimum age as 40 one years in the group of patients and maximum age as 74 years. In the group of controls, 41 years was the minimum age and we recorded as 76 years as the maximum age. We found insignificant relationship among different groups of ages and group of controls [Table-1]. A sum of 69.660% (n: 209) patients and 69.50% (n: 417) controls were males. Total 30.340% (n: 91) patients and 30.50% (n: 183) controls were females.

Table 1: Age-Wise Distribution of Study Subjects

S. No.	Age group in years	Cases (n = 300)	Control subjects (n = 600)	Total (n = 900)
1a	>40-50	105 (35)	210 (35)	315 (35)
2a	>50-60	163 (54.33)	326 (54.33)	489 (54.33)
3b	>60-70	25 (8.33)	50 (8.33)	75 (8.33)
4b	>70	7 (2.34)	14 (2.34)	21 (2.34)
Total		300 (100)	600 (100)	900 (100)

^b Parentheses show group-wise percentages.

Odds ratio = 1^a (a = S. no. 1: 2); odds ratio = 1^b (b = S. no. 3: 4) $X^2 = 0$; $df = 3$; $p = 1$; Not significant.

Total 66.670% (n: 200) patients and 65.0% (n: 290) controls were residents of urban regions, whereas 33.330% (n: 100) patients and 35.0% (n: 210) controls were from non-urban region. Among total 300 patients of Type-2 DM, only seventy-five patients displayed the positive history of the DM in their family. There was significant association of the positive past history of disease in the family with the prevalence of disease. Odds ratio as 0.560 stated the chance for the development of Type-2 DM was approximately 50.0% when compared with past positive history of the disease in their parents (Table-2).

Table 2: Family History of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Observed in Study Subjects

S. no.	Family history	Cases (n = 300)	Control subjects (n = 600)	Total (n = 900)
1a	Absent	225 (30.82)	50 (69.18)	730 (100)
2b	One parent	57 (45.23)	69 (54.77)	126 (100)
3b	Both parents	18 (40.9)	26 (59.1)	44 (100)
Total		300 (33.33)	600 (66.67)	900 (100)

^b Parentheses show group-wise percentages. Odds ratio = 0.56 (absent^a vs. present^b).

$X^2 = 11.24$; $df = 2$; $p = 0.003$; Significant.

Majority of the study population [48.670% (n: 438)] were performing only single or moderate physical activities, whereas 37.890% (n: 341) and 13.440% (n: 121) subjects of study were performing sedentary and vigorous physical activities correspondingly. We found a significant relationship of sedentary physical activity with the development of Type-2 DM (Table-3). In this current research work, there was absence of the past history of consumption of alcohol in all the female population.

Table 3: Physical Activity Observed in Study Subjects

S. no.	Physical activity	Cases (n = 300)	Control subjects (n = 600)	Total (n = 900)
1a	Sedentary/mild	137 (45.66)	204 (34)	341 (37.89)
2b	Moderate	122 (40.67)	316 (52.67)	438 (48.67)
3b	Vigorous	41 (13.67)	80 (13.33)	121 (13.44)
Total		300 (100)	600 (100)	900 (100)

^b Parentheses show group-wise percentages. Odds ratio = 1.63 (S. no. 1^a vs. S. no. 2^b + 3^b). $X^2 = 13.12$; $df = 2$; $p = 0.0014$; Significant.

Total 31.330% (n: 94) patients were users of alcohol. There was significant relationship of Typ-2 DM with the consumption of alcohol ($P < 0.050$) (Table-4). Only 5 females from the group of controls were cigarette smokers. A sum of total 38.330% (n: 115) patients and 29.0% (n: 174) controls were smokers. C 2-test showed the significant relationship of smoking with the prevalence of Type-2 DM. Most of the patients, 40.670% (n: 122), of this research work were in pre-hypertensive stage. Total 62 patients were suffering from HTN (Hypertension), among them fifty-two patients were in Stage-1 HTN and ten patients were in Stage-2 Hypertension. There was strong association of Hypertension with the development of Type-2 Hypertension (Table-5).

Table 4: Alcohol Consumption Observed in Study Subjects

S. no.	Alcohol consumption	Cases (n = 300)	Control subjects (n = 600)	Total (n = 900)
1a	Absent	206 (68.67)	458 (76.33)	664 (73.78)
2b	Present	94 (31.33)	142 (23.67)	236 (26.22)
Total		300 (100)	600 (100)	900 (100)

^bParentheses show group-wise percentages. Odds ratio = 1.37 (present^b vs. absent^a).

$X^2 = 6.961$; $df = 2$; $p = 0.0307$; Significant.

Table 5: Distribution of Study Subjects as Per Blood Pressure

S. no.	Blood pressure (mm Hg)	Cases (n = 300)	Control subjects (n = 600)	Total (n = 900)
1 ^a	Normal (<120/<80)	116 (38.67)	358 (59.67)	474 (52.67)
2 ^b	Prehypertension (120-139/80-89)	122 (40.67)	160 (26.66)	282 (31.33)
3 ^b	Hypertension stage 1 (140-159/90-99)	52 (17.33)	70 (11.67)	122 (13.56)
4 ^b	Hypertension stage 2(a160/a100)	10 (3.33)	12 (2)	22 (2.44)
Total		300 (100)	600 (100)	900 (100)

^pparentheses show group-wise percentages.

Odds ratio = 0.42 (normal^a vs. above normal^b).

$X^2 = 35.45$; $df = 3$; $p = <0.0000001$; Highly significant.

Most of the patients, 65.660% (n: 197), showed normal body mass index. Total 23.670% (n: 71) patients had overweight, whereas 8.0% (n: 24) patients were present with mild obesity. Total 2.70% (n: 8) patients were underweight. No patient was present with severe or moderate obesity. There is also positive association of Type-2 diabetes with BMI (Table-6).

Table 6: Distribution of Study Subjects as Per Degree of Obesity

S. No.	Degree of obesity (BMI = kg/m ²)	Cases (n = 300)	Control subjects (n = 600)	Total (n = 900)
1	< 18.5 (Underweight)	8 (2.7)	15 (2.5)	23 (2.56)
2	18.5-24.99 (Normal)	197 (65.66)	480 (80)	677 (75.22)
3	25-29.99 (Overweight)	71 (23.67)	75 (12.5)	146 (16.22)
4	a30 (Obese)	24 (8)	30 (5)	54 (6)
Total		300 (100)	600 (100)	900 (100)

Parentheses show group-wise percentages.

Odds ratio: 0.45 (BMI < 25 kg/m² vs. BMI a 25 kg/m²). $X^2 = 23.86$; $df = 3$; $p = 0.00002$; Highly significant.

DISCUSSION:

In this current research work, there was insignificant association between the age and the development of the Typ-2 DM. The research works conducted by Radzeviciene and Ostrauskas [8], Banerjee [9] and Bener [10] stated the similar association. One

research work conducted by West [11] stated the significant association of age groups with Type-2 DM, but the range of the age of the patients in that study was 10-22 years. This current research work stated female to male ratio as 30.340%:69.660 in patients' group and 30.50%:69.50% in the group of

controls. A research work conducted by Wang [12] examined the female to male ratio of 27.030:72.02% in the patients and 31.180%:69.82% in the control group. This ratio was 40.0%:60.0% in the research work conducted by Dutt [13]. In this current research work, there was strong association between the past histories of the disease in the family with the development of the disease. This finding is comparable with the results of various research works conducted by Radzeviciene and Ostrauskas [8], Banerjee [9], Wang [12], Dutt and Belmokhtar. Sedentary physical activity was significant risk factor associated with development of Type-2 DM in this research work. Wang [12], Dutt and Belmokhtar showed the same findings in their research works. Alcohol consumption was also a significant risk factor of disease in this research work [13].

Dutt and Bener stated the same results. Smoking was significant risk factor as examined by current research work. Similarly, research works conducted by Radzeviciene, Wang, Dutt stated the smoking as significant risk factor, whereas research works conducted by Poulton and Duc Son stated it as insignificant risk factor [14]. There was also positive association of HTN with the development of Type-2 DM. The research works conducted by Bener and Belmokhtar stated the similar findings but the research works conducted by Wang and Rama Lakshmi [10] declared it as insignificant risk factor for the development of disease. We found a strong association of BMI with the disease. Different research works provided the similar results.

CONCLUSION:

There was insignificant relationship between Type-2 DM and non-modifiable risk factors like gender and age except the past history of the disease in the family. Various modifiable risk factors like low physical activity, use of alcohol, obesity and hypertension were present with association with the Type-2 DM. thus, there are many causative agents of Typ-2 DM. There is no attribution of single cause for this disease.

REFERENCES:

1. Ramachandran A, Das AK, Joshi SR, Yajnik CS, Shah S, Prasanna Kumar KM. Current status of diabetes in India and need for novel therapeutic agents. *JAPI* 2010; 58:7–9.
2. Sayyad MG, Shahani AK, Pal S, Shirodkar JA, Gopal G. Computer simulation modelling for prevention of diabetes mellitus (prameha). *J Appl Sci* 2011;11(15):2670–9.
3. Shaw JE, Sicree RA, Zimmet PZ. Global estimates of the prevalence of diabetes for 2010 and 2030. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract* 2010;87(1):4–14.
4. WHO? Health Situation in the South- East Asia Region 1994–1997. New Delhi: WHO, Regional Office for SEAR, 1999.
5. Radzeviciene L, Ostrauskas R. Smoking habits and the risk of type 2 diabetes: a case–control study. *Diabetes Metab* 2009;35(3):192–7.
6. Sharma H, Chandola HM. Prameha in Ayurveda: correlation with obesity, metabolic syndrome, and diabetes mellitus. Part 1- etiology, classification, and pathogenesis. *J Altern Complement Med* 2011; 17(6):491–6.
7. Banerjee P, Ghosh MM, Biswas R, Bhattacharya SK. A study of risk factors of diabetes mellitus. *Indian J Community Med* 1993;18(1):48–50.
8. Bener A, Zirie M, Daghash MH, Al-Hamaq OAAA, Daradkeh G, Rikabi A. Lipids, lipoprotein (a) profile and HbA1c among Arabian type 2 diabetic patients. *Biomed Res* 2007;18(2):97–102.
9. West NA, Hamman RF, Liese AD, Zeitler PS, Mayer-Davis EJ, Daniels SR, et al. Cardiovascular risk factors among youth with and without type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care* 2009;32(1):175–80.
10. Canadian Diabetes Association. History of Diabetes. Available at: <http://www.diabetes.ca/about-diabetes/history-of-diabetes> (last accessed on September 10, 2015).
11. Wang L, Yamaguchi T, Yoshimine T, Katagiri A, Shirogane K, Ohashi Y. A case–control study of risk factors for development of type 2 diabetes. *J Epidemiol* 2002;12(6):424–30.
12. Dutt D, Roy G, Chatterjee P. Risk factor assessment for type II diabetes mellitus in a tertiary hospital in Kolkata. *Indian J Community Med* 2004;29(4):169–70.
13. Bilous R, Donnelly R. Introduction to diabetes. In: Bilous R, Donnelly R (Eds.). *Handbook of Diabetes*, 4th edn. UK: Blackwell Pub/John Wiley and Sons Inc, 2010. 3.
14. Belmokhtar F, Belmokhtar R, Sahi MD, Charef M. Risk factors associated with type 2 diabetes mellitus in west region of Algeria, Maghnia. *J Diabetes Metab* 2011;2(7):1–6.